

Selenium Heterocycles. Part VI Synthesis of 1,2-Diselenolo(3,4-b)Quinolines

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Reaction of 2-chloro-3-vinylquinolines with sodium hydrogen selenide in boiling ethanol gave the corresponding 1,2-diselenolo(3,4-b)quinolines. Likewise 2-chloro-3-(1',2'-dibromoethyl)-4-phenylquinoline furnished the corresponding 1,2-diselenolo(3,4-b)-quinoline through a novel debromination process. A reaction mechanism has been described.

RECENTLY we have reported¹ a serendipitous synthesis of the novel diselenolo(3,4-b)quinoline system. Survey of literature has revealed² that diselenium compounds, acyclic and cyclic, with adjacent selenium atoms are potential labilizing agents for lysosomes and mitochondria *in vitro*. In this paper we wish to report the synthesis and characterisation of a few hitherto unknown derivatives of the titled heterocycles and a viable mechanism for the unusual ring closure involved in this reaction.

The precursory compounds, 2-chloro-3-vinylquinolines (1a-1e)^{3,4} were obtained by reacting the respective 3-vinyl-2-quinolones with phosphoryl chloride. The chloroquinolines (1a-1e) on treatment with NaHSe in boiling ethanol furnished the corresponding diselenolo(3,4-b)quinolines (2a-2e) in good yields. The structures of the diselenoloquinolines were established by their elemental analyses and nmr spectra. A plausible mechanism has been demonstrated in the Scheme 1.

SCHEME I

- (a) $R^1 = \text{CH}_3$, $R^2 = \text{NO}_2$
 (b) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{H}$
 (c) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{CH}_3$
 (d) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{Cl}$
 (e) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{Br}$

From the mechanism depicted above, it is obvious that the presence of the vinyl functionality in (1) is an essential factor for a polar addition of hydrogen selenide anion across the vinyl double bond and consequential cyclisation to diselenolane ring with adjacent selenium atoms. Hence in a subsequent experiment the vinyl functionality in (1b) was saturated with bromine in chloroform and the resulting bromine adduct (3) was reacted with NaHSe in boiling ethanol. The intermediate (3) despite the fact it lacks the vinyl group also furnished the diselenoloquinoline (2b) as the major product (yield 52%) besides the selenoloquinoline⁵ (4) in 10% yield.

The formation of diselenoloquinoline (2b) in the above reaction should have become possible through a debromination of (3) to (1b) restoring the vinyl functionality in the molecule. Such a debromination by NaHSe is consistent in view of the debromination⁶ of vic-dibromides by sodium selenide. A minor part of the above reaction leading to the formation of selenoloquinoline (4) can be construed as occurring via a dehydrobromination sequence. From the quantities of the products obtained it is reasonable to conclude that in the intermediate (3) the tendency for debromination, followed by addition of hydrogen selenide anion across vinyl double bond and cyclisation to diselenoloquinoline (2b) is predominant.

Experimental

To a solution of sodium hydrogen selenide freshly prepared⁷ from equimolar amount of selenium

powder (0.8 g) and sodium borohydride (0.5 g) in ethanol was added the chloroquinoline (1a) (1.24 g). The mixture was then heated at reflux on a steam bath for 5 hrs. Thereafter the solution was evaporated and the residue was taken in chloroform and washed with water. The organic extract after drying (Na_2SO_4) was evaporated. Chromatography of the residue over basic alumina with petroleum ether furnished the product (2a) as red crystalline solid. (yield : 1.06 g, 57%, m.p. 111-112°). All other diselenoloquinolines (2b-2e) were prepared similarly and their m. ps, yields, nmr spectral data etc., have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—1,2-DISELENOLO(3,4-b)QUINOLINES

Compound	Yield %	m.p. (°C)	^1H . NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm
2a	57	111-112	1.92(d,3H,,3-CH ₃) J=7Hz 2.60(s,3H,4-CH ₃) 5.04(q,1H,9-H) J=7Hz 7.38-9.20(m,3H, Aromatic protons)
2b	64	134	1.79(d,3H,3-CH ₃) J=7Hz 4.43(q,1H,9-H) J=7Hz 7.10-8.00(m,9H, Aromatic protons)
2c	48	118-119	1.80(d,3H,3-CH ₃) J=7Hz 2.39(s,3H,6-CH ₃) 4.41(q,1H,9-H) J=7Hz 7.10-7.61(m,7H, Aromatic protons)
2d	54	144-147	1.81(d,3H,3-CH ₃) J=7Hz 4.48(d,1H,9-H) J=7Hz 7.20-8.12(m,8H, Aromatic protons)
2e	65	139-140	1.80(d,3H,3-CH ₃) J=7Hz 4.44(q,1H,9-H) J=7Hz 7.21-7.68(m,8H, Aromatic protons)

The elemental analysis of all the compounds agreed with the calculated values within the limits of experimental errors. All the compounds were recrystallised from petroleum ether (40-60). Melting points were determined on a Boetius micro-heating table and are uncorrected.

The nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian T-60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard.

The bromine-adduct (3) 1.82 g was heated with sodium hydrogen selenide prepared from selenium (0.8 g) and sodium borohydride (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) on a steam bath for 5 hrs. The solution was evaporated and the crude residue was taken up in chloroform and washed with water. The residue was chromatographed over basic alumina in petroleum ether when (2b) was obtained as red crystals. (yield : 855 mg, m.p. 134, 52%) The mixed m.p. with authentic sample undepressed.

Further elution of the column with benzene furnished 4-phenylselenolo(2, 3-b)quinoline (4) as pale yellow crystals. (yield : 123 mg, 10%, m.p. 127°). The mixed m.p. with authentic sample⁵ remains undepressed.

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References

1. T. K. RAJA and P. SHANMUGAM, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1977, 1581.
2. P. VAN CANEGHEM, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1974, **23**, 3491.
3. P. SHANMUGAM, K. KANAGARAJAN, N. SOUNDARARAJAN and A. GNANASEKARAN, *Synthesis*, 1976, 258.
4. P. SHANMUGAM, K. KANAGARAJAN, N. SOUNDARARAJAN, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1976, **B31**, 1685.
5. T. K. RAJA, S. NAGARAJAN and P. SHANMUGAM, *Chemica Scripta (Sweden)*, 1977, **12**, 44.
6. M. PRINCE, B. W. BREMER and W. BRENNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 4292.
7. D. L. KLAYMAN, T. S. GRIFFIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 197.